

Textile and Costume Traditions in Vajjika Manuscript Paintings

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Abstract

The study of textile and costume traditions provides critical insights into the cultural, social, and historical context of any civilization. This paper explores the depiction of textiles and costumes in Vajjika paintings, focusing on an illustrated manuscript of Tulsidas's Sri Ramcharitmanas housed in the Shri Sharda Sadan Pustakalaya, Lalganj, Vaishali, Bihar. By analyzing the garments, motifs, and adornments portrayed in these paintings, the study reconstructs possible weaving and dyeing techniques, material choices, and aesthetic preferences of the Vajjikanchal region in Bihar. The paper contextualizes the manuscript within the broader historical and geographical framework of the ancient Vajji confederacy, highlighting its connections with Jainism, Buddhism, and the artistic heritage of Mithila. Detailed examination of male and female attire, ranging from ascetic robes to royal ensembles, reveals distinct stylistic conventions, color schemes, and motif applications that distinguish Vajjika paintings from other Indian art traditions. The findings underscore the role of illustrated manuscripts as valuable repositories of historical textile knowledge and artistic expression. This research contributes to the growing discourse on indigenous artistic traditions, offering a foundation for further comparative analysis with extant textile specimens from the region.

Keywords

Textile and Costume Traditions, Vajjika Painting, Sri Ramcharitmanas, Vaishali, Vajjikanchal.

Introduction

Costumes of a civilization provide valuable insights into the thinking, tastes, and culture of its people. The costumes depicted in paintings offer a glimpse into the textiles prevalent during a specific era, reflecting the daily lives, environment, and influences of climate and history on the region. By comparing extant textiles with painted representations, plausible techniques and materials used for fabric creation can be inferred. This study focuses on the painted textiles of the Vajjika region in Bihar, specifically examining illustrations from a manuscript of Tulsidas's *Ramcharitmanas*, housed in the Shri Sharda Sadan Pustakalaya in Vaishali.

Objective of study

1. To study, analyse and highlight textile to show the garments of figures used in Vajjika manuscript paintings.
2. To explore the textile and garment tradition of the area through Vajjika manuscript paintings.

Review of Literature

For a thorough analysis a range of scholarly works were consulted to understand how textiles are depicted in Indian miniature paintings, how they can be identified, and where they were prevalent. Rapture: The Art of Indian Textiles by Rahul Jain provided insights into the evolution of textile techniques and designs across different regions and time periods [1]. The Art of Cloth in Mughal India [2] helped us analyze the representation of textiles in Indian art, particularly in relation to miniature paintings. To explore the cultural and religious significance of textiles, we referred to Ramayana by Valmiki and The Ramacharitmanas by Tulsidas [3], which contain vivid descriptions of fabrics worn by different characters, reflecting their status and identity. Additionally, Rosemary Crill's [4] work enriched our study with detailed research on textile patterns, weaving techniques, and their use in visual storytelling. These sources collectively enabled us to trace the historical and artistic significance of textiles in Vajjika art, examining their stylistic features, material composition, and contextual relevance within Indian miniature painting traditions.

Analysis

Vajjikanchal and Its Historical Context

The Land of the Vajjis

Vajjikanchal, locally referred to as *Bajjikanchal*, is the historical region of Vajji, one of the sixteen Mahajanapadas of ancient India. According to Buddhist and Jain texts such as the *Anguttara Nikaya* and the *Bhagavati Sutra*, the Vajji confederacy thrived in the 6th century BCE. Vajji was a union of eight clans, including the *Lichhavis*, *Videhas*, and *Gyatriks*, and was geographically bounded by the Gandak, Koshi, and Ganga rivers and the Himalayan range.[5]

Vaishali, the capital of Vajji, played a central role in Indian history. According to the Valmiki Ramayana, Vaishali was founded by Vishala, the son of King Ikshvaku and the celestial nymph *Alambusa*. Vaishali became a prominent site for both Jainism and Buddhism. Mahavira, the founder of Jainism, was born here, and the Buddha spent significant time in Vaishali, delivering sermons and announcing his impending *nirvana*[6]. The city's prominence extended to hosting the Second Buddhist Council in 383 BCE.

The Manuscript

The manuscript under study is an illustrated version of Tulsidas's Ramcharitmanas, handwritten in 1906 CE by Anchand Sahu Mali in the Kaithi script. Kaithi is a historical brahmic script that was used across parts of Northern and Eastern India such as Uttar-Pradesh, Bihar and Jharkhand.

The manuscript contains 773 pages, 153 of which feature full-page illustrations of episodes from the Ramayana. These paintings are distinct from other established Indian art forms and incorporate geometric motifs as decorative elements within the text.

This manuscript not only serves as a visual and textual retelling of Tulsidas's work but also highlights the convergence of literary devotion and artistic expression. It greatly advances our knowledge of the Bhakti movement and its cultural expressions in the Vajjikanchal region by providing a window into the artistic and spiritual priorities of its authors through its pictures. Furthermore, the manuscript depicts an artform lost to time. The manuscripts' artwork display an entirely novel art form that is distinct from existing Indian art styles. In a region where such traditions are not prevalent, a new kind of art and craft can be reintroduced with a complete revival of the lost painting style.

Medium and Surface

The illustrations were created on paper using water-based colors. However, certain paintings, such as the Rama Darbar from the Uttara-Kanda, exhibit a vibrant shine indicative of oil-based paints or a coat of varnish over it. Traces of oil on the reverse sides of these pages further support this hypothesis, suggesting the artist experimented with various techniques for visual effects.

Fig. 1 - Shiv- Parvati conversation at Mount Kailash

Subjects and Themes in the Illustrations

The manuscript's paintings vividly depict episodes from the *Ramacharitramanas* of Tulsidas with intricate details of human figures, animals, birds, plants, and mythical characters. The decorative motifs, including borders, and architectural patterns, enhance the manuscript's aesthetic appeal, showcasing the artist's creativity and skill.

Textile Depictions in Vajjika Paintings

Textiles

The figures in the manuscript are depicted in the fashion and style of their time, shaped by the climate and cultural practices of the region [7]. The predominant fabric seen in the paintings is cotton, which appears thick and stiff. These plain cotton textiles are likely adorned with motifs applied through block printing or stamping. Diaphanous fabrics are rarely depicted.

A diverse range of motifs is present, including trefoils, dots, and cross-hatching patterns. The clothing features small, repetitive designs such as dots, triangles, and geometric shapes, reminiscent of the traditional *Ajrak* and *Bandhani* textile styles [8]. *Ajrak* is a unique form of textile block printing in the Kutch district. The trefoil pattern found in many paintings and sculptures are a classic *Ajrak* motif. Interestingly, the trefoil motif is present in the shawl of the Priest-King of Mohenjo Daro. *Bandhani* is a type of tie-dye textile decorated by plucking the cloth into many tiny bindings that form a figurative design. It is mostly found in Gujarat and Rajasthan. *Bandhani* is clearly recognizable from the presence of dots on a fabric.

Fig. 2

The King, Princess and Shiva's Ganas

Fig. 3

Rama and Kakhbushandi

Costumes

Women's attire is primarily seen in two distinct styles. They wear a *stanpatta*, *kurpsika*, or *kanchuki*, paired with a *ghangra*, and complemented by an *odhani*, which may either flow freely or be tucked under the arms.

Men's clothing consists of an *antariya* and an *uttariya*, both secured with a *kambarband*. The *antariya* is draped in various ways—either draped over one shoulder and wrapped around the waist or placed over both shoulders from the front, with the ends hanging at the back.

Fig. 4
Mandodari - Rama Conversation

Male Figures

Hermits

Hermits, as spiritual and religious men, are depicted with a minimalist aesthetic, reflecting their ascetic lifestyle. Their upper bodies are typically bare, adorned only by symbolic elements such as the *Janayu* (sacred thread) or *Rudraksha Mala* (a necklace of sacred beads). The *Rudraksha Mala* is sometimes held in one or both hands, emphasizing their meditative and ritualistic practices.

Fig. 5
Sage Yajnavalkya and Sage Bharadwaj

Fig. 6
Hermit

Fig. 7.
Sage Bharadwaja

The lower garments of hermits, consisting of the dhoti or antariya, display notable variations:

In Figure 5, the antariya is a simple golden-yellow fabric, complemented by a contrasting green *kamarband* (waistband).

Figure 6 illustrates an even more austere style. The hermit wears only the *antariya* and *rudraksha mala*, omitting the *kamarband*. The golden-yellow *antariya* is embellished with trefoil motifs, which are scattered across the fabric.

Figure 7 portrays the sage Bharadwaj seated with folded legs. He wears a red *antariya* adorned with black trefoil motifs. Additionally, his bare upper body is marked with white *chandan* (sandalwood paste), signifying his spiritual devotion.

Divine Figures

Fig. 8
Shiva

Fig. 9
Vishnu

Fig. 10
Hanuman

The depiction of gods reveals their divine stature through the vibrancy and intricacy of their attire.

Figure 8 features the god Shiva. He wears a coordinated ensemble of yellow *antariya* paired with green *kamarbands*.

Figures 9 and 10 introduce patterned garments. In Figure 9, Vishnu's yellow *antariya* is adorned with red motifs, paired with a matching red *kamarband*. Meanwhile, Figure 10 portrays Hanuman wearing both an *uttariya* (upper drape) and an *antariya*. His yellow *antariya* features black motifs, and his blue *kamarband* matches the blue *uttariya*.

The gods are depicted barefoot, further emphasizing their sanctity. Their adornments include crowns, earrings, bangles, and occasionally necklaces, which enhance their regal and divine aura.

Royalty

Fig 14. Dashrath with his sons and their wives

Royal attire underscores status and grandeur.

1. Figure 11 shows King Bhanupratap on horseback, dressed in trousers and a shirt over which a crimson *uttariya* is elegantly draped. His attire, in golden yellow with black trefoil motifs, features a *kurta-pajama* style. The crimson *uttariya* is complemented by a matching hat reminiscent of those seen in Kalighat paintings.
2. Figure 12 depicts King Janak, Ram, and Lakshman wearing *antariyas* with uniform red fabrics and white motifs. Variety is introduced through differently

colored *uttariyas* and *kamarbands*.

3. Figure 13 offers a variant motif, replacing the trefoil pattern with a cluster of three dots. Lakshman's *antariya* includes a bordered design of thin, straight lines, providing additional texture.

Men

The clothing of commoners and nobles shows practical simplicity, with variations reflecting their social standing.

Common men wear either an *antariya* alone or pair it with a shirt and an *uttariya*.

The garments feature solid, contrasting colors such as crimson, deep blue, golden yellow, or aqua. Motifs, when present, are limited to black or white, ensuring an understated elegance.

Fig 15. Common men in Mithila

Fig 16. Men of Chitrakoot

Mythological Figures

Fig 17. Ravana

Fig. 18 Kakhushundi

The *vanaras* (monkeys) and bears are depicted without costumes, highlighting their animalistic nature. In contrast, gods and demons are attired in richly adorned *uttariyas* and *antariyas*, decorated with motifs such as trefoils or triangular clusters of three dots.

Female Figures

Fig. 19 Goddess Girija

Fig. 20 Goddess Uma

Goddesses

The goddesses are represented in opulent attire, befitting their divine status. Their ensembles typically consist of a *choli* (blouse), a *ghagra* or *antariya* (skirt-like lower garment), and an *odhani* (veil or drape).

The *choli* often features a three-dot motif, while the *ghagra* or *antariya* displays either the same pattern or a horizontal arrangement of v-shaped designs.

Vibrant colors and intricate patterns distinguish their divine identity.

Queens

Fig. 21 Sita

Fig. 22 Queen Mandodari

Fig. 23 Lakshmi

Fig. 24

Fig. 24

Fig. 25

Fig. 25

Royal women are shown in richly adorned garments, emphasizing their status and opulence.

Their attire comprises a *ghagra*, *choli*, and *odhani*, decorated with elaborate motifs. Contrasting color combinations—such as a green ghagra and choli paired with a red odhani (Figure 23)—highlight their regal taste.

Motifs include single dots, three-dot clusters, trefoils, and a four-dot flower-like pattern. The ghagras often feature a distinctive colored border with horizontal stripes, resembling lace.

Common Women

Fig. 26, 27 Common Women

The garments of common women, while simpler than those of royalty, retain a sense of elegance.

Patterns such as alternating dots and trefoils are common, with less frequent use of lace at the hem of their *ghagras*.

In Figure 27, tassels are depicted at the bottom of the *odhani*, adding a decorative yet functional detail.

Characterization of Pigments and their relation to textile

Manuscript paintings in India have always used a variety of natural pigments. The paintings of the Ramacharitamana's manuscript similarly use natural pigments for its colours. The natural pigments can be extracted from stone, insects or sometimes leaves. These materials are powdered and then mixed with gum resin or gum arabic using a mortar and pestle. This process leaves a fine paste which then is applied on paper.

Of the most commonly used colours one is scarlet red used variously in the manuscript, this was possibly extracted for Kerria Lac (also used in Lac bagels in the region) [9]. The Red Lac or Kerria Lac is found in Bihar from a resinous secretion called shellac, produced by the lac insect. Indian Yellow (a deep yellow) is used most commonly in clothing in the paintings. This colour was extracted possibly from the yellow ochre stone.

Interestingly, the manuscript uses a lot of secondary colors such as aqua green, rose pink and shades of yellow and cream. These colours were possibly made by mixing two primary colour pigments in various proportions with gum. The presence of these secondary colours is a defining characteristic of the Vajjika Manuscript paintings. These primary colours - scarlet red, indian yellow, indigo together secondary colours such as aqua green, rose pink, and cream make up a sophisticated colour palette which is used for animals, birds, human and mythological figures alike.

The use of these colors for textile however is of special interest. These colours are delightfully used to bring out the patterns and dyes of the fabric. White is used for bandhej, whereas motifs of ajrak and block print are drawn with green, red and blue. The trefoil motif is usually drawn in black over a cloth dyed in Indian yellow.

S.No.	Colours	Pigments	Paintings
1	Scarlet Red	Cinnabar (possibly imported), Red Lac - Kerria Lac	

2	Indian Yellow	Yellow Ochre stone	
3	Indigo	Indigo pigment	

4	Aqua Green	Malachite - in Naraul formation	
5	White	Kaolinite, Calcite - found in Bihar	

1. Artistic Techniques and Symbolism

The manuscript's illustrations highlight a mastery of visual storytelling, with solid-colored garments offset by intricate patterns. The use of geometric and floral motifs serves not only as decorative elements but also as indicators of the wearer's status and role. The absence of footwear among divine and spiritual figures emphasizes their connection to asceticism and spirituality, while the presence of jewelry underscores the wealth and power of royal and divine characters [10].

Conclusion

The Vajjika paintings provide a vivid representation of the textile traditions and cultural ethos of their time. Through meticulous depiction of garments, motifs, and adornments, these illustrations reflect the socio-economic hierarchies, religious beliefs, and artistic practices of the Vajjikanchal region. The use of vibrant colors, intricate patterns, and varied textile designs not only enhances the manuscript's visual appeal but also offers insights into the historical and cultural context of the era. This study underscores the significance of traditional art forms as invaluable resources for understanding the textile heritage of ancient India [11]. Future research may delve deeper into comparative analyses with extant textile specimens to reconstruct the techniques and materials used in Vajjika textiles.

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References

1. Jain, R. (2011). *Rapture: The Art of Indian Textiles*. New Delhi: Niyogi Books. Pp 54-55.
2. Houghteling, S. (2022). *The Art of Cloth in Mughal India*. Princeton University Press. Pp. 77.
3. Poddar, Hanumanprasad (2014). *Tulsidas' Ramcharitmanas*. Gorakhpur: Gitapress pp 223, 233, 335, 592.

4. Crill, R. (2015). *The Fabric of India*. Jamaica: Harry N. Abrams. pp16-17.
5. Mishra, Yogendra (1962). *An Early History of Vaishali*. Orient Book Distributors. Pp. 31.
6. Mishra, Yogendra (1985). *Homage to Vaishali*. Vaishali: Research Institute of Prakrit, Jainology and Ahimsa. pp311.
7. Mitter, Partha. (2001). *Indian Art*. Oxford : Oxford University Press pp. 115.
8. Jain, R. (2011). *Rapture: The Art of Indian Textiles*. New Delhi: Niyogi Books. Pp 54-55.
9. Chari, Celia & Eremin, Katherine & Jain, Anjali & Kim, Jinah & Newman, Richard. (2025). *Characterization of Indian pigments: investigating the color palette of a traditional Jaipuri workshop*. *Heritage Science*. 13. 10.1038/s40494-025-01729-4.
10. Mitter, Partha. (2001). *Indian Art*. Oxford : Oxford University Press pp. 76.
11. Prakash, V. (2016). *Crafts Atlas of India*. New Delhi: Niyogi Books. Pp 10-11.